

Challenges in promoting Paru-Paro Festival in Dasmariñas, Cavite as a tourist attraction

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Abstract

People travel far just to visit a particular tourist attraction. Visiting attractions could be the reason for their trip or a byproduct of their trip. Tourist attractions play an important role and integral part, especially in the tourism industry. It contributes to the economic benefits of tourism and promotes the local culture, heritage, and environment. This can often result in increased environmental preservation and a positive environmental impact on tourism. The overall purpose of this study is to determine the challenges in promoting the Paru-Paro Festival of Dasmariñas, Cavite as a tourist attraction. The Paru-Paro Festival can contribute to the city's tourism industry and can also bring and create more opportunities for the local government. The research method used for this study was exploratory and descriptive-qualitative research for this study. The researchers of this study developed an unstructured questionnaire as an instrument to gather data. The researchers conclude that there were ample challenges that the organizers encountered in preparing for the Paru-Paro Festival. On the other hand, most respondents disagreed with inadequate funding, lack of safety and protection, and inability to maintain cleanliness. This research serves as a tool for them to be informed about the challenges and guide them in possible solutions that can effectively promote the Paru-Paro Festival as a tourist attraction that will help attract more tourists and sustain the attraction itself.

Keywords: Challenges; Paru-Paro Festival; Dasmariñas, Cavite; Tourist attraction.

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Introduction

A tourist attraction is usually a place that tourists may want to see or visit for pleasure, interests, enjoyment, work, and educational purposes. There are different types of attractions; they can be natural, cultural, and manmade attractions. Natural attractions naturally exist globally, such as the sea, ocean, beaches, mountains, volcanoes, deserts, forests, waterfalls, lakes, and rivers. Tourists enjoy their visit or spend their vacation relaxing. Cultural attractions or heritage sites are usually located in urban areas wherein tourists may appreciate art in museums, galleries, and theaters. The cultural attractions also show beliefs, traditional values, historical places, monuments, and temples, while manmade attractions are a place of interest, such as theme parks, zoos, gardens, factories, and buildings that are made by humans (Great Zim Traveler, 2016).

A festival is an example of a cultural attraction. It is a traditional way of celebrating success or religious activities done by the local community within a period or day that conserves one's traditions and beliefs. The root of the word "festival" is "feast" ("fiesta"), which means celebration (Skoultzos et al., 2020). Sharma (2017) says that festivals are a way of connecting the people of the country and world to work and connect for a cause to spread solidarity, faith, love, respect, and duty between people. They are important occasions that are celebrated peacefully without destroying other emotions and beliefs.

According to Javier and Elazigue (2011), the role of local government units is to promote the social, economic, environmental, and cultural well-being of their communities, and their involvement in tourism must be related to that. The LGUs have the power to make their tourism plans, prioritizing over the medium to longer term with local authorities willing to contribute to community wellbeing. The plan must set out the following community outcomes because of tourism development, how these have been identified and how the local authority will contribute to these.

Festivals can create beautiful stories and memories, not only for the local people, but also for those tourists who will visit and attend the event. It may also make a good impression on potential tourists. They may want to visit a place that will contribute to the economic situation of the local government in a city, region, and the country itself. Against this rational backdrop, the researchers intend to study promoting a festival as a sustainable tourist attraction.

The overall purpose of this study is to determine the challenges in promoting the Paru-Paro Festival of Dasmariñas, Cavite as a tourist attraction. The Paru-Paro Festival can make a considerable contribution to the tourism industry of the city. It can also create more opportunities for the local government in the City of Dasmariñas.

Background of the Study

The City of Dasmariñas initially began as a barrio of Imus, Cavite, before it was officially recognized as a new town. There is an official event known as the Paru-Paro Festival that is celebrated on the 26th of November each year. This occasion represents the metamorphosis of a butterfly focusing on change, transformation, and celebration.

“The birth of a butterfly starts with an egg and becomes a butterfly larva where it proliferates. It sheds from its chrysalis and flies off to new life. The butterfly has a strong correlation to the city,” Mayor Jennifer Austria-Barzaga said. The significant transformation of Dasmariñas City from a minor barrio of Imus into a thriving municipality resembles the metamorphosis of a butterfly. The city has experienced significant changes, including various sectors and businesses, healthcare and learning institutions, residential areas, attractions for visitors, and infrastructure developments to enhance the economy.

The Paru-Paro Festival continues to show the city’s wholehearted willingness to embrace transformation and change just like butterflies. The festival is celebrated for featuring the metamorphosis of Dasmariñas from being a barrio to becoming one of the fastest developing cities in the country. One of the activities among them is a parade and street dance. It showcases the crafts and originality in the visual and performing arts. The significance of this is to develop an awareness of how tourism can help increase the well-being of people and protect the natural and cultural heritage. The Paru-Paro Festival has been celebrated for the past nine years, and there has been no study yet that can attract tourists and sustain the attraction.

Statement of the Problem

The main problem is to determine the challenges in promoting the Paru-Paro Festival of Dasmariñas, Cavite, as a tourist attraction. In conducting this research, it aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the participants?
 - a. Age
 - b. Gender
 - c. Occupation

2. What are the characteristics, opportunities, challenges, and strategies of the Paru-Paro Festival?

Foreign Literature

Festivals can support nearby communities by bringing in interesting visitors who will infuse modern income into the economy. Continued assessment of festivals is essential to guarantee they are meeting client expectations, creating positive word-of-mouth promotions and repeat visitations (Hugo & Lacher, 2014). Festivals can display and honor cultural traditions, as well as boost the local economy.

According to Ui et al. (2016), festivals and events are crucial tourism resources. To attend festivals and events, tourists visit the host community and tourism destinations. Tourism plays a vital role in stimulating a local economy in host communities. Hosting festivals and events in local communities is a common tourism development strategy. They attract tourists to the tourism destination, create tourism-related jobs, and disseminate economic benefits throughout the tourism destination. They provide recreational opportunities and pleasant visitor experiences for residents, affecting residents' quality of life. In any case, little has been written about almost the impact of festivals and local occasions on residents' quality of life.

According to Dewanarayana and Wimalaratana (2018), the number of travelers visiting Sri Lanka have increased rapidly since the Dutch and British periods along with the expansion of international transactions in the country. Many problems are encountered with facilities, prices at tourist attractions, the transportation that tourists use to visit other destinations, and accommodation for tourists. Sri Lanka is considered one of the most expensive tourist destinations in the world, with beaches in the South and West Coasts as the most visited tourist attractions. There is no extension of projects that would increase the costs, and proper management will cause enough income for them to maintain the site's image.

Bale is one of the largest zones in Oromia National Regional State and rich in natural and cultural tourism resources. With promoting and marketing, it is crucial to know the problems of places or tourist destinations. The travel and tourism industries are very competitive at local or international levels so that marketed businesses and destinations are likely to benefit. The promotion of some tourism destinations is essential for developing countries to strengthen the tourist destinations in Ethiopia. Marketing and promoting tourist destinations can help raise domestic and international inflows, leading to higher tourist receipts. The primary tools are advertising, sales promotion, public relations, direct marketing, and personal selling (Bayih & Tola, 2017).

According to Okharedia (2017), promoting tourism in developing economies offers challenges and prospects. To be sustainable, the tourism industry must be economical, especially in developing nations, to promote the destinations. It attempts to explore every challenge and prospect of promoting tourist spots in the developing economies of the nation. The study shows that the present challenges include: (a) the government's inability to formulate and implement progressive policies on tourism; (b) the current fight against terrorism; (c) unequal distribution of power and influence within the cultural divide; (d) structural imbalances in overall development patterns in developing economies; and (e) cultural clashes. In terms of prospects, this paper identified the following: (a) alleviation of poverty, (b) employment opportunity, (c) development of collective community income, (d) equitable management of resources between tourists and local people, and (e) the issue of corporate social responsibility. Tourism has become one of the world's leading industries, contributing significantly to the nation's gross domestic product (GDP) (Yu, 2012).

The industry has created jobs and contributes to foreign currency generation. It faces some impediments in physical infrastructure development, management, lack of information and communication technologies (ICTs), and marketing, and is also characterized by insufficient related rules and policies, high bank interest rates, erratic electricity, and high levels of corruption by government officials. Some issues that affect hospitality and the tourism industry are moreover getting changed with time. Tourism and hospitality operators demand change from strategic perspectives to give more attention to addressing current encounters and consider exploiting the opportunities (Sayed & Kanjee, 2013). The industry experiences large demographic fluctuations that involve changes in travel configurations and unpredictable financial situations, which are increasing the force on tourism and hospitality stakeholders to improve current promotions and industry strategies. Health and safety issues such as pandemics and global security concerns have increased the urgency for industry action (Kaonga, 2013). Barriers confronting the hospitality and tourism industries are multifaceted. Giving arrangements to these challenges will require a high level of harmonization and collaboration to rationalize resources more viably. However, challenging hospitality and tourism players will institute the needed yokes to guarantee the growth of a collaborative strategy in union with some more prominent and well-established global or national events so that long-term benefits will be realized throughout the nation (Jackson, 2017).

Festival events are recognized as effective strategies for host destinations to gain insight into the economic platform of the area. Festivals have increasingly been utilized as cultural tourism attractions and a compelling image maker for destinations. Proper marketing strategies can be made based on an improved understanding of tourists from the target market (Yang et al., 2011). Every society celebrates, and public celebration reflects the world view and the community's identity. Community is understood as the group that consists of locals and visitors that participate in the festival. Cultural festivals are events putting art values at the center of the festival. Festivals are special events just like before, but they are programs, concepts, and facilities are organized by professionals so that participants can experience the illusion of primary community (Zoltán, 2012).

Congcong (2014) stated that various regions hold many different types and content of festival activities, but setting up their own branded festival does not get the attention of the government at all. Research planning in creative festival tourism can better meet the demand of tourism consumers, improve the city's visibility, and drive the development of the regional economy, which further promotes the healthy development of festival tourism.

A full day of planning is suggested for more significant events, preferably two days if time allows, or they can be broken into smaller meetings over many days. Having these meetings periodically can help them report status and changes. It might be a good idea to have a "management retreat" at the same time as an intensive decision-making meeting (Coliat et al., 2016). Festivals are considered a part of event tourism, and they are emerging as a subfield mainly because they occupy a special place in each culture (Gomez-Casero et al., 2018).

Related Studies

There are few studies regarding cultural festivals. One of them is the Tinapay Festival that spotlighted the hardworking bakers in Cuenca. The festival includes bread-making contests and a festive parade to present the finished product of the bakers. It is celebrated sometime in June (Gonzales, 2017). Coliat et al. (2014) also added that people showcased the development of other people of Cuenca through industry. Professionals grew a number from bakeries. "*Mega Monay*," "*Malaking Semada*," "*Malaking Pandesal*," and "*Pinoy Pandesal*" were launched and displayed in the parade. The municipality planning and development department organizes the program to be used in the celebration of the Tinapay Festival. The owners of the bakeries sponsor the pastries/breads to be displayed and distributed during the event.

Festivals are events where local people can showcase their originalities, products, skills, and talents. It is an event that needs the support of the people and by the government. It requires planning to have a successful event where tourists will gain knowledge about the culture and tradition of the place or the event. It is crucial for festival management to monitor and evaluate visitor satisfaction to understand and identify the needs and perceptions of attendees, which in turn allows organizers to design and tailor the festival elements towards them, leading to higher visitor satisfaction, positive word-of-mouth advertising, and increased likelihood of repeat attendance (Lee et al., 2011).

According to Stankova and Vassenska (2015), festivals and other local special events are essential to widely acknowledge the economic development of areas to promote tourism, commercial outcomes, and increased investment in the host regions. Chang and Hsieh (2017) stated that the sustainable development of the festival depends on the support and participation of residents and tourists. Festivals are one of the fastest ways to promote tourism and promote local economic development. However, local communities find it difficult and cannot develop unique features and have sustainable development. Sustainable development of the festival has become a vital issue for host organizations. Research on traditional festival activities mainly focuses on analyzing economic issues and benefits.

Tourism is one of the world's major industries, experiencing a deepening diversification and constant growth to have significant expansion. An ever-increasing number of tourism destinations worldwide are open to the opportunity to make tourism a key driver of socio-economic progress through the creation of jobs, export revenues, and infrastructure development. Despite the different occasional challenges, international tourist arrivals have shown continuous growth – from 25 million in 1950 to 278 million in 1980, 528 million in 1995, and 1.087 billion in 2013 (World Tourism Organization, 2014). Tourism has become one of the leading players in international commerce and a significant source of income for many developing countries. It is a complex industry, only if it is still recognized for its contribution to generating revenue, investment, and overall growth in country production because of foreign exchange.

Festivals made each town or city or even the province itself famous. People believe that festivals contribute to the promotion and marketing of that town. These promotional strategies generate more tourists and can add to the cultural and economic growth of that area. Festivals are like “products”; they should be well recognized and properly promoted to attract local and international tourists. Festivals should take pride when they invite Filipinos to visit foreign tourists and experience the local festivals in the area. Celebrations like this likewise became an integral part of the international cultural and social fabric. It was celebrated from times immemorial, just like the Ati-Atihan Festival of Aklan, which started in the year 1212, patronized not just by locals but also by international visitors. In Batangas, Koreans had the greatest number of tourist arrivals all year round. These foreign tourists in every celebration of festivals add to the growth of the tourism industry locally and internationally.

Festivals have a significant impact on the development of cultural tourism for the host communities. Organizers have been using historical and cultural themes to develop the annual events to attract visitors and create a cultural image in the host cities by holding festivals in community settings. The desire for festivals and events is not explicitly designed to address the needs of any group. Event hosting is often developed based on tourism and economic opportunities for social and cultural benefits (Buena et al., 2014). Many researchers have contested that local communities play a vital role in the development of tourism through festivals (Alampay et al., 2018; Alejandria-Gonzalez, 2016; Del Rosario, 2019; Mesana et al., 2021).

Events can generate a vast amount of tourism when they cater to visitors, grants, or sponsorships of direct or indirect intent. The government supports and promotes events as part of its strategies for economic development, nation-building, and cultural tourism. The events, in turn, are a vital tool for attracting visitors and building an image within different communities. Tourism-related services, including travel, accommodation, restaurants, shopping, are the primary beneficiaries of the event.

According to Ladanga et al. (2018), in promoting festivals, there are a lot of communication methods involved in the process of preparing for the festival. Various communication methods associated with the festival can help them communicate the interaction of messages and people, along with the foundation of participation, commitment, and interest. Communication through social media also plays a vital role in promoting the festival itself. Emotions with previously defined symbols influence the beliefs of others through informational messages, ideas, opinions, and feelings of an individual or community in an interaction. Participation is a collection of communities wherein the residents have similar interests and live within the same area. Determining the community's level of participation would somehow identify whether the community event or project held or officiated by the organizers will be considered a failure or a success (Balderas Torres, 2014). Participation in the community includes communication and utilization of information. It would provide a better understanding of the individuals from the activities of the community event wherein their participation is sought. The importance of the festival to the community plays a significant role in the image and reputation of the local government. It is also based on how residents communicate and gather their surroundings throughout society.

According to Luna (2015), governments have different strategies to finance the festivals, mainly through entrepreneurship, investments, incentives, and subsidies. They also play an important role at the planning level by regulating and coordinating efforts with local actors. Money interventions carried out by government agencies are mostly returned as taxes, but people are also beneficiaries to improve the infrastructure created for festival needs. The festival can be improved if it is considered a local community trademark, mega event, or institution. Sometimes, the public sector is a great investment, but always to get higher revenues or benefits back, both on the economic and social sides. Festivals are considered as contributors to the cultural tourism of a place. Foreign and local studies also tackle how festivals are celebrated, promoted, planned, and organized. This will serve as a tool and guide throughout the current study, which is about the challenges in promoting festivals to become tourist attractions.

Methodology

The research method used for this study was exploratory and descriptive-qualitative research for this study. This method is appropriate to this study because it gathers information and aims to find out the objective of this research. The study was conducted in the City of Dasmariñas, Cavite. A total of 100 participants are randomly selected from those involved in promoting the Paru-Paro Festival, such as the organizers, the tourism officers, and the Local Government Unit of Dasmariñas. The researchers of this study developed an unstructured questionnaire as an instrument to gather data. This questionnaire consists of respondents' personal information and has a series of questions regarding their experience while promoting the festival.

Results and Discussion

Demographic Profile

Figure 1 shows that 52% of the respondents who answer the survey are females, while 48% are males.

Figure 1. Gender of the respondents

Figure 2. Age of the respondents

In figure 2, it shows that 10% of the respondents' ages 18-22 years old, while 22% of the respondents' ages 29-31 years old, 31% are ages 32 and above, and lastly the 37% of the respondents aged 23-28 are the highest who answered the demographic profile.

Figure 3. Offices of the respondents

Figure 3 shows the percentage of the respondents who participated in the survey conducted through their departments/offices. The highest percentage of the respondents are working in general service, which is 15%, 12% for the tourism office, 11% for the administrative department, 10% for the engineering, 9% for Operations Management (OM), Centralized Pension Processing Centre (CPPC), Organization Behavior (OB), and Human Resource Management (HRM) offices, and 8% for the Red Cross and Security.

PARU-PARO FESTIVAL EXPERIENCE

Figure 4. Paru-Paro Festival Experience of the Respondents

In figure 4, it shows the number of years the respondents have experienced the Paru- Paro Festival. 11% of the respondents experienced the festival 7-9 years, 42% of the with 1-3 years, and the highest percentage is 47% with 4-6 years.

Characteristics, Opportunities, Challenges, and Strategies of the Paru-Paro Festival

CHARACTERISTICS OF PARU-PARO FESTIVAL

Figure 5. Characteristics of the Paru-Paro Festival

In figure 5, it answers the characteristics of the Paru-Paro Festival. The first question shows that 45% of the respondents agreed that the Paru-Paro Festival is informative. In question 1.2, 62% strongly agreed that the festival provides entertainment. In question 1.3, it states that the mentioned festival reminds them of their culture and tradition, with 42% strongly agreeing with the statement. In question 1.4, 53% of the respondents strongly agreed that the mentioned festival develops social interaction. Lastly, question 1.5 shows that 55% responded that the mentioned festival promotes enthusiasm and harmony.

OPPORTUNITIES OF PARU-PARO FESTIVAL

Figure 6. Opportunities for Paru-Paro Festival

In figure 6, it answered the opportunities of the Paru-Paro Festival. In question 2.1, 46 out of 100 respondents agreed that Paru-Paro Festival can boost the economy of Dasmariñas. Question 2.2 shows that 50% agree that the festival can create job opportunities. Question 2.3 shows that 53% of the respondents strongly agree that the Paru- Paro Festival can attract tourists and visitors. In question 2.4, it shows that 52% agreed that the festival can generate revenues for communities. In question 2.5, it shows that 46% agreed that the festival can improve the environment.

CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED IN PARU-PARO FESTIVAL

Figure 7. Challenges encountered in Paru-Paro Festival

In figure 7, it answered the challenges encountered in Paru-Paro Festival. In question 3.1, about 37% of the respondents agreed that the venue is not wide enough to accommodate tourists. In question 3.2, 48% disagreed that the festival is poor at funding. In question 3.3, there are 59% who disagreed that the festival lacks safety and protection. In question 3.4, 43% of the respondents are neutral that Paru-Paro Festival causes traffic congestion. Lastly, in question 3.5, about 44% of the respondents disagreed that this festival is unable to maintain cleanliness.

Figure 8. Strategies that can promote Paru-Paro Festival

In figure 8, it states the strategies that can promote Paru-Paro Festival. For question 4.1, 46% of the respondents agreed in creating a website. In question 4.2, 50% of the respondents answered agree in the use of social media. In question 4.3, 45% of the respondents answered agree in creating posters, fliers, and tarpaulins. In question 4.4, 60% of the respondents agreed in making community partnerships, while in question 4.5, 45% of the respondents answered both strongly agree and agree in making tourism blogs.

Based on the data presented, the researchers found that the demographic profile of the respondents was divided into three (3) aspects, which consist of their age, offices, and Paru-Paro Festival experience. According to the data, most respondents are between 23 and 28 years old from different departments, with the majority working in general service. Most of the respondents experienced the Paru-Paro Festival for four to six years.

Many of the respondents answered the characteristics of Paru-Paro Festival, and most of them strongly agree that Paru-Paro Festival is informative that can be shared with every attendee, provides entertainment for all the people who watch the festival, reminds people about their culture and tradition, develops social interaction, and promote enthusiasm and harmony.

Most of the respondents agreed with the opportunities of the Paru-Paro Festival, that the festival would boost the economy of Dasmariñas, create job opportunities, attract tourists and visitors, generate revenues for communities, and improve the environment. The Paru-Paro Festival will benefit from it and strengthen the communities by enriching their quality of life as a town.

Respondents agreed that the venue is not wide enough to accommodate tourists. The respondents disagreed about the poor funding, lack of safety and protection, and inability to maintain cleanliness. However, the respondents answered neutrally that the festival causes traffic congestion. Challenges are unavoidable when having a festival, and by providing solutions right away, it will surely be a success.

Respondents also agreed with the strategies promoting the Paru-Paro Festival. This includes creating a website, using social media, giving posters and flyers, making a community partnership, and making vlogs or blogs. The respondents believe that in this way the festival will be more well known and become successful.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The researchers conclude that there were ample challenges that the organizers encountered in preparing for the Paru-Paro Festival. Most of the respondents agreed that the event's venue is not enough to accommodate visitors, and it also causes traffic congestion. These common challenges can affect the event, since lots of people value their time and efforts. Traffic is indeed time-consuming; instead of enjoying the event in their allotted time, visitors might be stuck in the area because there are numerous people and vehicles. Aside from the traffic, the area is also not that wide enough to accommodate people, which results in a long queue of vehicles.

On the other hand, most respondents disagreed with inadequate funding, lack of safety and protection, and inability to maintain cleanliness. This means that Paru-Paro Festival has enough funds to support its programs and activities. People love to attend activities because it makes the event memorable and fun. There are marshals, security, emergency kits, and ambulances that control the crowd and provide first aid during the event. Some departments were responsible for maintaining the City of Dasmariñas before, during, and after the event. This is also necessary because they wanted to make the event and the environment presentable in the eyes of every visitor.

The Paru-Paro Festival also promotes opportunities for the people and the economy. This event can create various jobs, improve the environment, and attract tourists and visitors. Having a massive number of visitors can affect the revenues of the community. It also boosts the economy of Dasmariñas since tourists will notice what the city can offer. The researchers highly recommend this to the people of the study, the Local Government Unit of the city of Dasmariñas, Cavite. This research serves as a tool for them to be informed about the challenges and guide them in possible solutions that can effectively promote the Paru-Paro Festival as a tourist attraction that will help attract more tourists and sustain the attraction itself.

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